

SPECIFICITY OF POLYVALENT DIAGNOSTIC SERUM OF INTESTINAL YERSINIOSIS OF HOMOLOGOUS MICROORGANISMS

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Annotation. The article presents the results of an analysis of the specificity of hyperimmune sera obtained from the blood of experimental animals immunized with O3 and O9 serotypes of *Yersinia enterocolitica* on homologous microorganisms using the glass and test tube agglutination reaction. It was found that hyperimmune sera obtained from experimental animals vaccinated with the O9 serotype of *Yersinia enterocolitica* have high specificity to homologous microbes.

Key words: intestinal yersiniosis, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, polyvalent serum, agglutination reaction.

To date, there are no interventions that are sufficiently effective to reduce the incidence of intestinal yersiniosis in humans. This situation, in turn, requires the study of the epidemiological characteristics of intestinal yersiniosis and the improvement of laboratory diagnostics[1].

The aim of the study is to assess the specificity of polyvalent diagnostic serums of intestinal yersiniosis obtained from experimental animals on homologous microorganisms.

The research materials were strains of O3 *Yersinia enterocolitica* 005011/659 serovar O9, *Yersinia enterocolitica* 005008/656 and hyperimmune serums from immunization stages

Yersinia enterocolitica O3 and O9 were inactivated, prepared in various concentrations, administered to experimental animals (rabbits) and created a bank of hyperimmune rabbit serums against the pathogens of intestinal yersiniosis from rabbits (72 samples-variants): preimmunization, 1-5 post-immunization serums.

An experimental series of diagnostics from strains of O3 *Y. enterocolitica* 00501/659 and O9 *Y. enterocolitica* 00508/656 serovar was prepared in a concentration of 15 billion in the Research and Production Department of RIEMUPKIATM. Polyvalent serums before immunization, as well as after 1-, 2-,

3-, 4- and 5-fold vaccination, were investigated by the method of agglutination reaction on object glasses and test tubes using diagnostics of the experimental series.

Before immunisation, the blood serum of experimental animals of all groups was examined using the agglutination reaction and the results were negative. This condition indicates that the body of experimental animals has not been in contact with *Yersinia enterocolitica*[2].

After the first immunisation (day 7) in the blood serum of animals of group I, group II, group II, group II, group II, group II, group II and group I that received serovar *Y. enterocolitica* 005011/659, antibodies were not detected. O3, after the second immunisation (day 14), all rabbits developed antibodies against the administered antigens. From the 21st day of immunisation, i.e. after the 3rd immunisation, the average geometric titre of the agglutination reaction in the samples has increased significantly. On the 35th day of immunisation (after the 5th immunisation), the average arithmetic titre of antibodies in serums obtained from experimental animals by experimental series diagnostics prepared from strains of *Y. enterocolitica* 005011/659 serovar O3 ranged from 1:252 to 1:800.

The average titre of antibodies ranged from 1:2016 to 1:5080 in the study of blood serums obtained from experimental animals at the immunisation stages using strains of serovar O9 *Y. enterocolitica* 00508/656 as an experimental diagnosis by agglutination reaction.

This, when checking the specificity of hyperimmune serums obtained from the blood of experimental animals immunized with O3 and O9 *Yersinia enterocolitica* serovars at the stages of immunisation with homologous microorganisms using an agglutination reaction in target glasses and test tubes, the specificity of hyperimmune serums was tested at the immunisation stage with homologous microorganisms. obtained from experimental animals immunised with O9 *Yersinia enterocolitica* with homologous microbes was high.

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